

Bis Heterocycles as Possible Fungicides

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Twelve bis-thiosemicarbazides, twelve bis-(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-alkanes, twelve bis-(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes and four bis-(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes have been synthesised. Some of them have been screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* and found to be antifungal.

THIOSEMICARBAZIDES have been reported to possess antibacterial¹, antifungal², antitubercular³ and anticonvulsant⁴ properties. Keeping this in view we have synthesised some 4,4'-diaryl bis oxalyl/malonyl/succinyl/adipyl thiosemicarbazides.

Compounds containing triazole ring are reported to possess pesticidal⁵, insecticidal⁶, fungicidal⁷ and bactericidal⁸ activities. Keeping this in view we have synthesised some bis-(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-alkanes.

Substituted thiadiazoles have been reported to display fungicidal⁹, nematocidal¹⁰ and antiinflammatory¹¹ activities. In view of these some bis-(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes have been synthesised. Substituted oxadiazoles were reported as antimitotic¹², antifungal¹³, muscle relaxants¹⁴ and tranquilizing¹⁴ agents. Keeping this in view we have synthesised some bis-(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes.

4,4'-Diaryl bis oxalyl/malonyl/succinyl/adipyl thiosemicarbazides (I) have been synthesised by the condensation of acid hydrazides and aryl isothiocyanates. I on treatment with MeOH (8%) yielded bis-(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-alkanes (II) and with conc. H₂SO₄, bis-(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes (III). The acid hydrazides were heated with CS₂ and KOH in methanol to yield bis-(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes (IV). Compounds thus prepared are given in Tables 1-4 alongwith their fungicidal data. Compounds 13, 14 and 15 of Table 2, 25, 26 and 27 of Table 3 and 37 of Table 4 are not bis-alkanes but have been described and shown under the bis-alkane series for obvious reason.

Experimental

The purity of the resultant compounds was checked by tlc. Melting points are uncorrected. The structures of the compounds were checked by ir and elemental analysis.

4,4'-Diaryl bis oxalyl/malonyl/succinyl/adipyl thiosemicarbazides (I): A methanolic solution of an acid hydrazide (0.1 M) and arylisothiocyanate

(0.21 M) was refluxed for 4 hr and cooled. The solid separating out was filtered, washed and recrystallised. Compounds thus prepared are given in Table 1.

Scheme

n=0,1,2,4 ; R = Anisyl (OP), P = phenetyl, benzyl

Bis-(4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-alkanes (II): Thiosemicarbazide (I) (0.01 M) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (8%, 50 ml) to a clear solution (4 hr) and cooled. It was poured into cold water and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with cold dil. hydrochloric acid. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised. Compounds thus prepared are reported in Table 2.

Bis-(5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes (III): Thiosemicarbazide (I) (0.01 M) was dissolved in ice cold conc. sulphuric acid (10 ml). The resulting solution was kept at room temp. for 2 hr, stirred at intervals and then poured over crushed ice. It was stirred, diluted with water and filtered. The residue obtained was washed and recrystallised. Compounds thus prepared are given in Table 3.

Bis-(5-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-alkanes (IV): An acid hydrazide (0.01 M) was mixed with a 10 ml aqueous solution of KOH (0.02 M). To this, 100 ml methanol was added. A clear solution was thus obtained. Carbon disulphide (2 M) was now added to it and the resulting solution refluxed for 6 hr. It was concentrated to a small volume and then poured into ice-water. It was filtered and

TABLE 1—4,4'-DIARYL Bis OXALYL/MALONYL/SUCCINYL/ADIPYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDES (I)

Sl. No.	R	n	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		Fungicidal activity (Concn. 10 ppm)		
						N	S	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
1	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	0	200	87.6	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	18.64 (18.75)	14.15 (14.28)	—	—	—
2	Benzyl	0	205	84.8	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	20.07 (20.19)	15.25 (15.38)	25.7	26.2	27.5
3	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	0	206	85.9	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	17.54 (17.64)	13.90 (13.44)	—	—	—
4	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	1	100	80.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	18.10 (18.18)	13.75 (13.85)	—	—	—
5	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	1	210	86.0	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	18.07 (18.18)	13.72 (13.85)	26.3	26.0	28.3
6	Benzyl	1	200	88.3	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	19.42 (19.53)	14.76 (14.88)	—	—	—
7	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	2	212	81.0	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	16.55 (16.66)	12.58 (12.70)	26.5	27.0	29.4
8	Benzyl	2	201	85.6	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	18.80 (18.92)	14.20 (14.30)	—	—	—
9 ^a	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	2	202	85.5	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	16.52 (16.66)	12.61 (12.70)	27.6	27.8	29.7
10	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	4	209	79.5	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	16.52 (16.66)	12.61 (12.70)	26.5	27.6	29.5
11	Benzyl	4	211	89.7	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	17.68 (17.79)	13.43 (13.55)	27.8	28.0	30.4
12	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	4	202	10.0	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	15.66 (15.79)	11.92 (12.03)	—	—	—

IR spectral data in ν_{max} in cm⁻¹

N-H Stretching
3200

Secondary - CONH
1680

-C=S
1110

paradisubstituted benzene
830

TABLE 2—Bis-(4-ARYL-5-MERCAPTO-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-3-YL)-ALKANES (II)

Sl. No.	R	n	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		Fungicidal activity (Concn. 10 ppm)		
						N	S	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
13	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	0	295	72.3	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	20.26 (20.38)	15.42 (15.53)	35.5	35.8	36.8
14	Benzyl	0	>250	75.6	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂	22.00 (20.10)	16.73 (16.84)	—	—	—
15	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	0	310	70.7	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	18.97 (19.09)	14.43 (14.54)	36.2	36.0	37.3
16	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	1	>250	74.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	19.59 (19.72)	14.97 (15.02)	36.5	36.7	38.3
17	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	1	>250	81.2	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	19.60 (19.72)	14.98 (15.02)	36.4	36.8	38.5
18	Benzyl	1	>250	79.2	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₆ S ₂	21.20 (21.32)	16.21 (16.24)	—	—	—
19	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	2	>250	78.6	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	19.00 (19.09)	14.40 (14.54)	—	—	—
20	Benzyl	2	>250	77.6	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₆ S ₂	20.47 (20.59)	15.57 (15.68)	—	—	—
21 ^b	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	2	290	80.5	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	17.82 (17.95)	13.55 (13.67)	—	—	—
22	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	4	>250	75.8	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	17.83 (17.95)	13.56 (13.67)	38.0	38.3	39.2
23	Benzyl	4	>250	80.0	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ S ₂	19.15 (19.26)	14.55 (14.68)	—	—	—
24	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	4	240	79.6	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	16.81 (16.93)	12.78 (12.90)	38.5	38.7	40.4

IR spectral data ν_{max} in cm⁻¹

Secondary -NH
3350

Conjugated cyclic system -C=N
1500

C=S
1160

paradisubstituted benzene
810

TABLE 3—Bis-(5-ARYLAMINO-1,3,4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL)-ALKANES (III)

Sl. No.	R	n	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		Fungicidal activity (Concn. 10 ppm)		
						N	S	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
25	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	0	207	90.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	20.28 (20.38)	15.42 (15.53)	—	—	—
26	Benzyl	0	240	92.2	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	21.98 (22.10)	16.72 (16.84)	—	—	—
27 ^c	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	0	195	95.6	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ S ₂	19.00 (19.09)	14.42 (14.54)	40.5	42.0	44.5
28	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	1	>250	92.3	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	19.60 (19.72)	14.98 (15.02)	—	—	—
29	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	1	215	93.7	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	19.58 (19.72)	14.96 (15.02)	—	—	—
30	Benzyl	1	101	95.4	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ S ₂	21.20 (21.32)	16.12 (16.24)	—	—	—
31	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	2	>250	91.5	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	18.98 (19.09)	14.40 (14.54)	44.3	44.5	46.3
32	Benzyl	2	205	94.6	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ S ₂	20.47 (20.59)	15.54 (15.68)	43.7	44.0	45.6
33	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	2	285	94.5	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	17.82 (17.95)	13.56 (13.67)	45.0	44.8	47.4
34	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	4	>250	89.0	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	17.83 (17.95)	13.54 (13.67)	—	—	—
35	Benzyl	4	195	93.7	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₆ S ₂	19.15 (19.26)	14.56 (14.68)	47.3	48.2	49.5
36	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	4	210	93.8	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	16.80 (16.93)	12.78 (12.90)	47.7	48.0	50.7

IR spectral data ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹

c	Secondary -NH 8320	Conjugated cyclic system -C=N 1490	paradisubstituted benzene 810
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TABLE 4—Bis(5-MERCAPTO-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-YL)-ALKANES (IV)

Sl. No.	n	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		Fungicidal Activity (Concn. 10 ppm)		
					N	S	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
37	0	>250	58.7	C ₄ H ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	27.60 (27.72)	31.54 (31.68)	32.5	32.0	32.8
38	1	276	75.0	C ₅ H ₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	25.79 (25.92)	29.50 (29.68)	33.0	33.4	34.7
39	2	196	65.4	C ₆ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	24.24 (24.35)	27.70 (27.82)	33.8	33.7	35.3
40 ^d	4	206	80.5	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	21.58 (21.70)	24.68 (24.80)	34.0	34.5	36.0
							75.5	74.6	72.8
							78.5	79.5	78.3

MEMCGE
BLITOX 50 WP
(Commercial fungicides)IR spectral data ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹

d	Secondary -NH 3150	Conjugated cyclic system -C=N 1510	-C=S 1175
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the filtrate acidified with dilute HCl. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallized. Compounds thus prepared are given in Table 4.

Fungicidal screening :

The compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity by agar growth technique^{15,16} against three fungi viz. *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. Sacchari*. The diameter of the fungus colony was measured at three different concentrations viz. 1 : 1,000, 1 : 10,000 and 1 : 100,000. Inhibition of fungus growth was determined on the basis of the difference in growth between control plates and those treated with the toxicant. The fungicidal activity of tested compounds was compared with that of two commercial fungicides viz. BLITOX

50 WP and MEMCGE using similar conditions and the same fungus strains.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds screened were found to be antifungal. They were nearly equally effective against all the three fungi and the presence and position of the different groups did not show any marked effect towards antifungal activity.

Thiosemicarbazides (I), the parent compounds were least active and compounds derived from them showed better antifungal activity. Thiadiazolyl alkanes (III) were found to be more active than triazolyl alkanes (II) which showed higher antifungal activity than oxadiazolyl alkanes (IV), In

each series the antifungal activity showed a slight increase as the number of $-CH_2$ group increased.

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References

1. R. P. BHAMARIA, R. A. BELLARE and C. V. DELIWALA, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1968, **6**, 62.
2. R. B. PATHAK, B. JAHANA and S. C. BAHREL, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Agents.*, 1980, **8**, 12.
3. R. S. VERMA, K. C. GUPTA, AMERNATH and V. S. MISHRA, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1964, **4**, 63.
4. A. K. SEN GUPTA, K. C. AGARWAL and M. MUSHTAQ, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17B**, 184.
5. A. G. Farbenfabriken Bayer, *Belg. Patent*, 1964, 644, 164; *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **63**, 9991a.
6. TONY ORBALO, *Ger. Offen.*, 1970, **2**, 029, 375; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **74**, 76428u.
7. G. HEUBACH, B. SACHSE and H. BUERSTELL, *Ger. Offen.*, 1980, 2,826, 760; *Chem. Abs.*, 1980, **92**, 181200h.
8. S. C. BENNUR, V. G. JIGAJINNI and V. V. BADIGER, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1976, **21**, 757; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **85**, 94306j.
9. S. P. SUMAN and S. C. BAHREL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 374.
10. W. MAYER, B. BOEHNER and D. DAWES, *Ger. Offen.*, 1974, 2,418,363; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **82**, 31328k.
11. TSUNGY SHEN, R. L. CLARK and A. A. PRESSOLANO, *S. African Patent*, 1976, 7503, 527; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **86**, 72662r.
12. D. GHIRAM, SCHWARTZ and I. SIMITI, *Farmacologia*, 1974, **22**, 141; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **82**, 43274c.
13. G. L. MAHESHWARI, R. P. MAHESH and P. SINGH, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 549.
14. J. PIALA and H. L. YALE, *U. S. Patent*, 1964, 3,141,022; *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **61**, 83176.
15. U. S. D. A. Circular No. 198, 1931.
16. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, **5**, 357.